

Exploring Figurative Language Usage in Contemporary Music: Pedagogical Implications for English Language Instruction

Büşra ARAS¹, Sultan BOZKURT² & Serap ÖNEN³

¹ İstanbul University-Cerrahpaşa, İstanbul, TÜRKİYE
busra.aras@iuc.edu.tr

ORCID: 0009-0006-6046-4650

² İstanbul University-Cerrahpaşa, İstanbul, TÜRKİYE
sultan.bozkurt@ogr.iuc.edu.tr

ORCID: 0000-0003-2841-7476

³ Corresponding Author, İstanbul University-Cerrahpaşa, İstanbul, TÜRKİYE
onens@iuc.edu.tr

ORCID: 0000-0001-7738-1938

Article information

Submission	20/05/2024	Revision received	11/08/2024
Acceptance	02/09/2024	Publication date	22/10/2024

Keywords:

Figures of speech
Song
Music
Language teaching

Abstract: This research aimed to scrutinize and delineate the figures of speech manifesting in English hit songs. A selection of songs from Spotify's Top 30 Hit Songs List was chosen as the study material. The study employed a qualitative content analysis approach to classify the type and calculate the frequency of the figures of speech within the corpus of English hit songs. The results of this study revealed 200 figurative speech examples in our small-scale corpus, which comprised 8352 words. This suggests a prevalence of figurative language use within English-language songs. While metaphors and hyperboles were the most frequently used figures of speech, apostrophes, and understatements were the least common. The results underscore the linguistic richness of hit songs, advocating their inclusion in English language teaching (ELT) classrooms, particularly for vocabulary instruction.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Söz sanatları
Şarkı
Müzik
Dil öğretimi

Çağdaş Müzikte Söz Sanatlarının Kullanımı: İngilizce Dil Eğitimi için Pedagojik Çıkarımlar
Özet: Bu araştırma, İngilizce hit şarkılarda ortaya çıkan söz sanatlarını incelemeyi ve tasvir etmeyi amaçladı. Çalışma materyali olarak Spotify'nın en iyi 30 hit şarkı listesinden bir şarkı seçkisi seçildi. Çalışma, İngilizce hit şarkıların derlemi içindeki söz sanatlarının türünü sınıflandırmak ve sıklığını hesaplamak için nitel bir içerik analizi yaklaşımı kullanmıştır. Bu çalışmanın sonucu 8352 kelimedenden oluşan mini derlemimizde 200 söz sanatı örneği olduğunu ortaya çıkarmıştır. Bu, İngilizce şarkılarda söz sanatları kullanımının yaygın olduğunu gösteriyor. Metaforlar ve abartılar en sık kullanılan söz sanatları iken, tecvîh-i kelimeler ve arıksayış en az kullanılanlardır. Sonuçlar, popüler şarkıların dilsel zenginliğini vurguluyor ve bu şarkıların İngiliz Dili Eğitimi sınıflarına, özellikle de kelime öğretimine dahil edilmelerini önermektedir.

To Cite This Article: Aras, B., Bozkurt, S., & Önen, S. (2024). Exploring figurative language usage in contemporary music: Pedagogical implications for English language instruction. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 18(2), 29–51. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13860646>

1. Introduction

Language is crucial to human identity and is closely linked to our thought processes, reasoning, self-reflection, and the development of advanced civilizations. Hence, the structure of language, shaped by its applications, is adaptable and flexible, capable of conveying all human communication. Language is also structured to take advantage of human creativity, evident in word games, puns, and puzzles. Furthermore, humans use language creatively when they innovate new expressions or use words in novel ways (Genetti, 2014). A language style unique to its users is evident in written or spoken forms, such as literary works or speeches. One of the most ingenious ways of using language imaginatively is through poetry. As Kennedy and Gioia (1994) suggested, “There are other elements in a poem besides plain prose sense: sounds, images, rhythms, figures of speech. These may strike us and please us even before we ask” (p. 6). A poem is often compared to a puzzle written in secret code, with a message cleverly hidden. However, the impact of a poem on the reader’s mental and emotional state goes beyond just a message. Through its musical qualities and implications, a poem can also influence the reader’s subconscious (Kennedy & Gioia, 1994).

It is often the case that poetry tends to be more memorable than regular speech. This effect is further amplified when it is combined with music. As Kennedy and Gioia said, “We usually meet poems as words on a page, but songs we generally first encounter as sounds in the air” (p. 118). As a result, songs are often written in simple language that can be easily understood upon first hearing. However, certain songwriters have created songs that require close and repeated attention to their lyrics. Beginning in the 1960s with artists such as Bob Dylan, Leonard Cohen, Joni Mitchell, and Frank Zappa, some pop songwriters crafted intentionally complex songs. Sting, Robert Smith, Bono, and Suzanne Vega have also written lyrics that can be considered complex and full of unique, dreamlike imagery. It may be beneficial for a listener to play the recording multiple times to comprehend the lyrics entirely. It is worth noting that literary criticism is not solely an academic enterprise, as high school and college students often engage in discussions about the lyrics of their favorite songs (Kennedy & Gioia, 1994). Hence, understanding the message hidden in figures of speech can create a quality discussion environment for language learners and enrich the learning environment by making it more motivating and creative for ELT teachers.

1.1. Figures of Speech

Figures of speech have been defined in various ways in the literature. Al-Qudsy (2016) describes them as “linguistic elements that have non-literal meanings” (p. 8). Thwala et al. (2019) offer a broader definition, describing them as “the use of words in an unusual way to denote conciseness, definiteness, emphasis, and wisdom” to concretize abstract concepts and experiences (p. 1). Joshi (2014) notes that figures of speech involve interpreting a word or phrase to represent a different concept, aiming to elicit a specific effect in the audience. Regmi (2014) states that figures of speech enhance the beauty and effectiveness of language. Dancygier and Sweetser (2014) argue that figurative language adds aesthetic value to texts, especially poetry. Quinn (1982) points out that writing differs from chemical engineering; we should not study figures of speech like the periodic table. Instead, we are exploring real potentialities within language and ourselves. ‘Figures of speech’ reveal language’s limitless flexibility, showing how we can use it creatively, as Shakespeare did, and how we might do the same.

Kennedy and Gioia (1994) define figures of speech as instances where a speaker or writer departs from usual word meanings for freshness or emphasis. They argue that figures of

speech are not devices to state falsehoods but often convey truths that literal language cannot and emphasize these truths. Arp and Perrine (2004) add that figurative language, which uses figures of speech, should not be taken literally. While scholars provide various definitions and categorizations of figures of speech, this study will follow the categories proposed by Kennedy and Gioia. They identify eleven primary types: simile, metaphor, personification, apostrophe, hyperbole, understatement, metonymy, synecdoche, transferred epithet, paradox, and pun (*paronomasia*).

A simile is a comparison between two objects denoted by a verb like “resembles” or a connective like “as,” “like,” or “than,” conveying a likeness. However, for a simile to exist, the objects being compared must differ in kind. For instance, stating, “Your fingers are like mine,” is a literal statement, not a simile. Conversely, using a simile to say, “Your fingers are like sausages,” is appropriate (Kennedy & Gioia, 1994, p. 98). Metaphor implies a comparison by substituting or identifying a figurative term with a literal one (Arp & Perrine, 2004). Glucksberg (2001) views metaphor as a conceptual portrayal, where an object symbolizes another, often abstract, object—a representation. It asserts that something is something else, figuratively speaking. Unlike a simile, a metaphor can convey a broader range of similarities, often highlighting multiple traits uniting two objects. For instance, while the metaphor “He eats like a pig” compares eating habits, saying “He’s a pig” may draw parallels between morality and appearance (Kennedy & Gioia, 1994, p. 99). Personification is attributing human qualities to an animal, object, or idea. It essentially falls under the category of metaphor, involving an implied comparison where the figurative term always pertains to a human being (Arp & Perrine, 2004). For instance, “The wind stood up and gave a shout” (Kennedy & Gioia, 1994, p. 104). The apostrophe is closely linked to personification and involves addressing someone absent or deceased or something nonhuman as if they were present, alive, and capable of responding to the speaker’s words (Arp & Perrine, 2004). It is a way to breathe life into the inanimate. As in the stirring lines of an American spiritual, “Death, ain’t you got no shame?” It is a method of giving body to the obscured and communicating to it personally (Kennedy & Gioia, 1994, p. 105). Overstatement, or hyperbole, is essentially exaggeration, yet it is an exaggeration used to pursue truth. It can be used to give various effects. “It may be humorous or grave, fanciful or restrained, convincing or unconvincing” (Arp & Perrine, 2004, p.47). For instance, “I’ve told him a thousand times.” Exaggerating for effect is a primary motivation for the use of hyperbole, as John Burgon described Petra as “A rose-red city, half as old as Time.” It is also used for humor, as in the blues song where a large woman boasts, “Every time I shake, some skinny gal loses her home.” (Kennedy & Gioia, 1994, p. 105). Understatement is the ability to understate or exaggerate a truth to highlight it is mutually exclusive (Arp & Perrine, 2004). Saying less than one means or understating oneself can occur in both one’s words and delivery. It is the opposite of hyperbole, in which what is implied is more than what is said. Robert Frost’s poem “Birches” serves as a good illustration. The last line of the poem suggests that swinging on a birch tree is one of life’s most profoundly fulfilling experiences of all times (Kennedy & Gioia, 1994, p. 105). Metonymy is when the name of one thing is used in place of another closely related to it. “It substitutes some significant detail or aspect of an experience for the experience itself” (Arp & Perrine, 2004, p. 33). For instance, “The White House decided” means the president made the actual decision (Kennedy & Gioia, 1994, p. 106). Synecdoche is the usage of the component throughout the entire (Arp & Perrine, 2004). It is similar to metonymy, yet a synecdoche is when an aspect of anything is used to represent the entire thing or the other way around. As Kennedy and Gioia (1994) suggest, “She lent a hand” means she gave her whole being, not only her hand (p. 106). A transferred epithet is another type of metonymy. It is a literary strategy of emphasis wherein the poet assigns a quality of

one item to another that is closely related to it. As Dutta and Talukder (2022) expressed, it is a figurative device in which an adjective is linguistically connected to another noun in the phrase rather than one that it semantically modifies. A paradox is a remark that seems contradictory at first but makes sense after some thought (Kennedy & Gioia, 1994). Arp and Perrine (2004) state that a paradox's worth is determined by its shock value. The reader is instantly drawn in by its seeming impossibility, which also highlights how true what is being said is due to its seeming absurdity. Pun is the "play on words" (Kennedy & Gioia, 1994, p. 107). "It exploits multiple meanings or similar-sounding words for humorous or rhetorical effect" (Dutta & Talukder, 2022, p. 9). For instance, "I can't conceive, madam, can you?" in response to a question on distinguishing between men and women. 'Conceive' may have two different connotations in the previous example: "to comprehend" or "to be pregnant," making particular references accordingly (Kennedy & Gioia, 1994, p. 107).

1.2. Prior Research on Figurative Language

A literature review indicated that numerous research studies have been conducted on using figures of speech in song lyrics. Santika and Syafradin (2023) conducted a study focusing on the figures of speech types in the lyrics of Taylor Swift's latest album. Their analysis covered thirteen songs, identifying a total of 96 examples of figures of speech. They used the classification of Leech (2013), who suggests eight types of figurative language. Metaphors emerged as the most prevalent type of figurative language, followed by simile, metonymy, hyperbole, and personification successively. Oxymoron, litotes, and irony were the least frequent ones. In a similar study, Sondakh et al. (2023) investigated the figurative language in one of Demi Lovato's albums. Their qualitative descriptive study utilized Miles and Huberman's framework (1994) to analyze the data. The results revealed that metaphor is the most frequent figure of speech type, followed by hyperbole, personification, and simile. Likewise, Julianto et al. (2023) focused on the figurative language in Billie Eilish's songs in "Don't Smile at Me." Leech's theory (1981) was employed to classify the meaning of the songs. The results revealed the emergence of seven figurative language types— allusion, metaphor, hyperbole, irony, metonymy, personification, and simile, with metaphor being the most prevalent. Moreover, conceptual and connotative meanings were commonly observed in the songs. Finally, Barung et al. (2023) examined the figures of speech in Coldplay songs. Their findings revealed five types of figures of speech—simile, metaphor, personification, metonymy, and hyperbole—with hyperbole being the most prevalent. Additionally, as Leech (1981) proposed, connotative meaning was observed.

The current study aims to analyze the figures of speech found in English hit songs based on the Spotify Top 30 Hit Songs List. The study focuses on identifying the most prevalent figures of speech utilized within these hit songs, drawing upon Kennedy and Gioia's (1994) theory of figures of speech. Subsequently, the study offers insights into the pedagogical implications of incorporating these figures of speech into ELT classrooms. Songs are chosen as the basis of this study as they are enduring literary works that significantly impact language retention. Many individuals can recall even the most trivial songs they heard in childhood or years past. Recognizing the power of songs in education and the mnemonic aid provided by rhythm and melody, this study examines global hit songs for their use of figurative language. The rationale for selecting English songs is that English serves as the global lingua franca. An analysis of the 2023 global hit songs revealed that twenty-five of the top thirty songs are in English, further justifying the focus on English-language songs. With all these in mind, this study seeks answers to the following research question: What prevalent figures of speech are evident in the popular English musical compositions 2023?

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

This is a qualitative descriptive study that employs content analysis. As a course of its nature, content analysis requires “a relatively low level of interpretation” (Vaismoradi *et al.*, 2013, p. 2). Additionally, this technique involves methodically coding and classifying vast volumes of textual data unobtrusively to identify word usage trends and patterns, frequency, interactions, and communication structures and discourses (Mayring, 2000; Pope *et al.*, 2006). Therefore, this approach is deemed appropriate for the current study to examine song lyrics and determine the frequency of figures of speech in popular hit songs of 2023.

2.2. Data Source

This small-scale corpus study comprises a total of 8,352 words drawn from the lyrics of the top 25 English hit songs worldwide. The primary source of information is the Spotify database, as Spotify has recently become the most popular audio streaming service in the world, with 226 million premium members across 184 countries and a total of 574 million users (Monga, 2024, May 17). The songs were chosen upon the release of the Spotify 2023 30 Global Hit Songs List from the official website on November 29, 2023. Five of the songs featured in the Global Top 30 List are in Spanish; consequently, they have been omitted from the analysis. Instead, the examination focused on the remaining twenty-five songs. The study's corpus consists of the songs listed in Table 1.

Table 1.

The list of hit songs analyzed

Song Name	Number of Words	Artist(s)
1. Flowers	125	Miley Cyrus
2. Kill Bill	271	SZA
3. As It Was	226	Harry Styles
4. Seven (feat. Latto)	504	Jung Kook, Latto
5. Cruel Summer	415	Taylor Swift
6. Creepin' (with The Weeknd & 21 Savage)	445	Metro Boomin, The Weeknd
7. Calm Down (with Selena Gomez)	399	Rema, Selena Gomez
8. Anti-Hero	337	Taylor Swift
9. I Wanna Be Yours	238	Arctic Monkeys
10. I'm Good (Blue)	263	David Guetta, Bebe Rexha
11. Die For You	433	The Weeknd
12. Unholy (feat. Kim Petras)	297	Sam Smith, Kim Petras
13. Boy's a liar Pt.2	335	Pink Pantheress, Ice Spice
14. Daylight	333	David Kushner
15. Another Love	293	Tom Odell
16. Starboy	452	The Weeknd, Daft Punk
17. Cupid- Twin Ver.	292	FIFTY FIFTY
18. I Ain't Worried	255	OneRepublic
19. Here With Me	177	d4vd
20. Last Night	382	Morgan Wallen
21. Golden Hour	195	JVKE
22. Until I Found You (with Em Beihold)- Em Beihold version	173	Stephen Sanchez, Em Beihold
23. Paint the Town Red	742	Doja Cat
24. Sweater Weather	351	The Neighborhood
25. Snooze	419	SZA

2.3. Data Collection and Analysis

The lyrics are taken from the Internet and copied into distinct web papers. In contrast to other qualitative methodologies, data analysis in qualitative descriptive research is not based on pre-existing hypotheses. Instead, as codes are generated from the data throughout the study, qualitative descriptive research depends entirely on data. These studies also tend to be defined by concurrently collecting and analyzing data, much like other qualitative research methodologies (Lambert & Lambert, 2012). Although different academics define and classify figures of speech differently, this study will adhere to Kennedy and Gioia's categories. They identify the eleven main categories: simile, metaphor, personification, apostrophe, exaggeration, understatement, metonymy, synecdoche, transferred epithet, paradox, and pun (paronomasia). The selection of Kennedy and Gioia's (1995) framework was motivated by their distinctive approach to defining song lyrics. They consider song lyrics to be a form of poetry and elaborate that while no element of a poem functions independently, poetry can be dissected into its constituent parts, such as tone, irony, literal meaning, suggestions, imagery, figures of speech, sound, and rhythm. They assert,

Long analyses of metrical feet, rime schemes, and indentations tend to make ponderous reading: such formal and technical elements are perhaps the hardest to discuss engagingly. And yet formal analysis (at least a little of it) can be interesting and illuminating: it can measure the very pulse beat of lines (p. 1818).

Therefore, this study, aiming to enhance the teaching of figures of speech through popular songs in foreign language classrooms, limits its focus to the most common types of figures of speech, considering this sufficient for the intended educational purpose. Unlike linguists and literary experts, who are well-versed in all existing figures of speech, English learners at this level only need to grasp the connotations and denotations of words and phrases. Thus, Kennedy and Gioia's framework was deemed appropriate for this study. Following the framework selection, the lyrics were continuously read to comprehend their context and meaning, enabling their identification and classification within the framework. Then, the frequency of each figure of speech appearing in the songs was calculated. At times, there was a need to check cultural and contextual references to interpret the connotation better. Each researcher independently conducted a thorough analysis of all the lyrics. Regular meetings and discussions were held among the researchers to ensure coding consistency. Any discrepancies were then addressed through negotiations until a consensus was reached.

3. Findings

In the analyzed data, consisting of a total of 8352 words, 200 instances of figurative speech were identified, indicating the pervasive use of figurative language in English songs. All the figurative speech samples proposed by Kennedy and Gioia (1994) were observed in the data. While metaphor is the most frequent one (38%), apostrophe (1%) and understatement (1%) are the least frequent ones in the corpus. Table 2 below summarizes the findings of the study, from the most frequent to the least frequent ones, hierarchically.

As can be seen, metaphor is the most frequent figurative speech type in the songs, followed by hyperbole and paradox. Moreover, when we examine the number of figures of speech in each song, it is noticeable that all songs include examples of figurative language. There are at least five instances of figures of speech in each song. Moreover, six of the songs contain more than ten examples of figures of speech. When we consider the limited length of the songs and the existence of repeat parts at least two times in each song, it can be asserted that songwriters benefit from the figures of speech. The overall results reveal that figures of

speech use are very common in popular songs. Examples of each figure of speech type found in our small corpus are presented and interpreted from the following.

Table 2.

Frequency Table of the Figures of Speech Samples in the Songs

Figures of Speech	Frequency <i>f</i>	Percentage %
1. Metaphor	76	38
2. Hyperbole	40	20
3. Paradox	23	11.5
4. Personification	18	9
5. Simile	13	6.5
6. Metonymy	9	4.5
7. Synecdoche	9	4.5
8. Pun	5	2.5
9. Transferred Epithet	3	1.5
10. Apostrophe	2	1
11. Understatement	2	1
TOTAL	200	100

3.1. Metaphor

The analysis of the hit songs of 2023 revealed that metaphor is the most prevalent type of figurative speech, as observed in previous studies. In twenty-four out of the twenty-five songs, figurative speech samples were identified, with frequencies ranging from 1 to 7.

Table 3.

Metaphors

Song	Name of the Song & Singer(s)	Metaphor
1	Flowers by Miley Cyrus	“We were good, <u>we were gold</u> ”
9	I Wanna Be Yours by Arctic Monkeys	“I wanna be your <u>vacuum cleaner</u> <u>Breathing in your dust</u> ”
4	Seven by Jung Kook and Latto	“ <u>Weight of the world</u> on your shoulders”
5	Cruel Summer by Taylor Swift	“ <u>Shiny toy with a price</u> You know that I bought it”
6	Creepin’ by Metro Boomin and The Weeknd	“Somebody said they saw you The person you were kissing wasn’t me And I would never ask you, I just kept it to myself I don’t wanna know, <u>if you’re playing me</u> ”
7	Calm down by Rema and Selena Gomez	“Baby, calm down, calm down Girl, <u>this your body e put my heart for lockdown</u> ”
8	Anti-hero by Taylor Swift	“I have this thing where I get older but just never wiser. <u>Midnights become my afternoons</u> ” <u>Take a look inside your heart</u> , is there any room for me?”
13	Boy’s a Liar pt.2 by Pink Pantheress and Ice Spice	I won't have to <u>hold my breath</u> 'til you <u>get down on</u> <u>one knee</u> Because you only want to hold me when I'm looking <u>good enough</u> ”
14	Daylight by David Kushner	Telling myself I won't go there Oh, but I know that I won't care <u>Tryna wash away all the blood I've spilt</u> ”
18	I Ain’t Worried by OneRepublic	I ain't worried 'bout it right now (right now) <u>Swimmin' in the floods (hey!), dancing on the clouds</u> <u>below</u>

Song 22 is the only song in a metaphor that could not be observed in the lyrics. On the other hand, Song 9 and Song 14 emerged as the compositions with the highest number of metaphorical instances. In total, 76 instances of metaphor were identified in the songs, comprising 38% of the figurative language samples within the dataset. Due to the large number of metaphorical examples in the song lyrics, ten instances selected from various songs will be presented, with detailed interpretations provided for five of them.

The first example of metaphor is observed in Song 1 in the first line: “*We were good, we were gold*” (Cyrus et al., 2022). This line suggests a period of excellence or prosperity. It implies that things were going very well in their relationship, akin to precious gold. Using “gold” suggests that their relationship was precious and valuable, meaning it was successful.

The following lines are from Song 9, where the speaker metaphorically aligns themselves with the vacuum cleaner, indicating a desire for intimacy and closeness with the addressee, seeking deeper involvement in their life.

*I wanna be your vacuum cleaner
Breathing in your dust. (Clarke, 1982)*

In other words, they express a deep desire to be intimately close to someone, even if it means absorbing their flaws or being in their shadow. The vacuum cleaner is a metaphorical expression here, suggesting a willingness to take in everything about the other person, including their shortcomings or the residue of their past experiences. It conveys a longing for connection and a willingness to accept someone completely, including his/her imperfections.

Another example of metaphor appears in Song 4. The underlined part, “*Weight of the world,*” is used here to represent a heavy burden or some responsibility.

Weight of the world on your shoulders (Wotman et al., 2023)

“*Weight of the world on your shoulders*” is a common metaphorical expression describing a feeling of immense pressure or responsibility. It suggests that someone feels burdened by a significant amount of stress, worry, or obligation, as if they are carrying the weight of all the problems in the world. This phrase is often used to empathize with someone dealing with a heavy load of challenges or difficulties in their life. Likewise, an example of metaphor can also be seen below in Song 5.

*Shiny toy with a price
You know that I bought it (Swift et al., 2023)*

“*Shiny toy with a price*” is the metaphorical expression in these lines. Describing a person as a shiny toy implies that they are perceived as attractive and desirable, yet engaging with them entails certain costs and challenges within the relationship. Even though a relationship with this person is appealing, it brings some sacrifices and potential drawbacks. The last sample of metaphor to be discussed here is from Song 5:

*Somebody said they saw you
The person you were kissing wasn't me
And I would never ask you, I just kept it to myself
I don't wanna know, if you're playing me (Wayne et al., 2023)*

These lyrics express a sense of betrayal and hurt in a relationship. The speaker acknowledges that rumors are circulating about their partner. However, they avoid confronting their partner directly. "I don't wanna know if you're playing me" reflects a reluctance to confirm the truth due to the potential emotional distress it may bring. The speaker would rather remain in denial than face the reality that their partner may be unfaithful or deceitful. It encapsulates the fear of being deceived and the desire to avoid further heartbreak by maintaining a state of ignorance. In a nutshell, it can be said that a metaphorical expression is used to imply betrayal and disloyalty in the underlined part of the lyrics.

3.2. Hyperbole

Hyperbole is the exaggerated expression of thoughts and feelings for a special effect (Kennedy & Gioia, 1994). Analysis of the global hit songs of 2023 in the English language revealed that hyperbole is the second most frequent type of figurative language in the songs, which appeared in twenty of them. Only in five of them, which are Song 9, Song 12, Song 13, Song 14, and Song 17, no examples of hyperbole are observed. Song 11 (*Die for You by The Weeknd*) has the highest number of hyperbole examples, 5 in total. In total, there are forty examples of hyperbole in these twenty-five songs. Descriptive statistics show that 20% of the figurative language examples are hyperbole. There are numerous examples of hyperbole in the dataset, and since it is impossible to present them all here, the table below shows ten examples from different songs and detailed discussions for five of them.

Table 4.
Hyperboles

Song	Name of the Song & Singer(s)	Hyperbole
3	As It Was by Harry Styles	<u>In this world, it's just us</u>
11	Die for You by The Weeknd	Even though we're going through it And it makes you feel alone Just know that <u>I would die for you</u> I don't want none, I just want you <u>If I can't have you, no one should</u>
2	Kill Bill by SZA <u>I might kill my ex</u> , I still love him though <u>Rather be in jail than alone</u> And I screamed for whatever it's worth <u>I love you, ain't that the worst thing you ever heard?</u>
5	Cruel Summer by Taylor Swift <u>Killing me slow</u> , out the window I'm always waiting for you to be waiting below <u>I don't need no light to see you</u>
21	Golden Hour by JVKE	Shine It's your golden hour (oh)
22	Until I Found You by Stephen Sanchez and Em Beihold	<u>I was lost within the darkness</u> , but then I found her
23	Paint the Town Red By Doja Cat	<u>Money really all that we fiendin' for</u> (walk on by)
16	Starboy by The Weeknd, Daft Punk	House so empty, need a centerpiece <u>Twenty racks a table cut from ebony</u>

To begin with, "In this world, it's just us" in Song 3 (Styles et al., 2022) bears a hyperbolic meaning. Being the only people in this world is a widespread exaggerated hyperbolic

expression. The songwriter may have used it to express the feeling of belonging to each other or the dependency of the addresser on the addressee. Additionally, it can be interpreted that the speaker wishes to emphasize the sole importance of the addressee, with the rest of the world being of no significance.

Secondly, in Song 11, a hyperbolic expression is observed, as can be seen in the lyrics below:

*Even though we're going through it
And it makes you feel alone
Just know that I would die for you* (Tesfaye et al., 2017)

These lyrics emphasize the strong bond between partners in this relationship, even though they have been experiencing some hardships lately. In the third line, the underlined expression “I would die for you” is a hyperbolic expression to express love and commitment. It conveys the willingness to make the most significant sacrifice for the other person's sake, emphasizing the relationship's depth of affection and commitment. It reassures them that their relationship can survive every difficulty and that they will stand by each other through thick and thin.

The third sample of hyperbole is from Song 2.

*I don't want none, I just want you
If I can't have you, no one should* (Rowe et al., 2022)

These lines suggest the dependency of one partner to the other one emotionally. The underlined sentence is an exaggerated expression of the feelings. The speaker wants to stress their commitment and jealousy. It is an extreme level of possessiveness, and it suggests that if the speaker is not the desired partner, then the addressee should not be with anyone else either. It is an unrealistic expectancy, and hyperbole is used as a type of figure of speech to make the situation's illogicality more vivid. The speaker might want to express the depth of their feelings of jealousy, insecurity, or fear of losing the person they love. It reflects a sense of ownership over the partner and a reluctance to let them go, even if it means preventing them from finding happiness elsewhere.

Another example of hyperbole can be seen in the lyrics of Song 2 below:

*I might kill my ex, I still love him though
Rather be in jail than alone* (Rowe et al., 2022)

“Killing the ex” and “Rather be in jail than alone” are hyperbolic sayings. The speaker, who has a problematic state of mind, tries to show their intense feelings of love, longing, and desperation. “Killing the ex” is an extreme expression of the tumultuous emotions that can accompany the end of a relationship. “Rather be in jail than alone” underscores the depth of loneliness and emotional pain the speaker is experiencing. It implies that the idea of being imprisoned is preferable to facing the emotional emptiness of being alone. This highlights the speaker's fear of abandonment and their desperate need for connection and companionship, even if it means sacrificing personal freedom. The songwriter benefitted from hyperbole, which made the lyrics more striking and dramatic. The last example of hyperbole is from Song 5. In the lines below, the exaggeration of the impact of “I love you” as the worst thing that happened is a hyperbolic sentence. The speaker acknowledges that the declaration of love in this relationship can be terrifying because it bears the risk of rejection.

And I screamed for whatever it's worth
I love you, ain't that the worst thing you ever heard? (Swift et al., 2023)

3.3. Paradox

Paradox constitutes 11.5% of all the figurative language samples in our corpus. There are twenty-three examples of it in our study in fourteen songs, meaning that paradox is another type of figurative language that songwriters mostly prefer. Ten examples of it are presented in the table below, and five of them will be discussed.

Table 5.
Paradoxes

Song	Name of the Song & Singer(s)	Paradox
		<u>“What doesn’t kill me makes me want you more”</u>
	
5	Cruel Summer by Taylor Swift	“It’s cool, that’s what I tell ’em No rules in <u>breakable heaven</u> ”
		I’m drunk in the back of the car And <u>I cried like a baby coming home from the bar</u> (oh)
18	I Ain’t Worried by One Republic	<u>“I’ll take it in and let it go”</u>
6	Creepin’ by Metro Boomin and The Weeknd	“But baby keep it to yourself <u>I don’t wanna know, if you’re playing me”</u>
		<u>“I got a girl but I still feel alone”</u> “I’m so mature, I2m so mature <u>I’m so mature, I got me a therapist to tell me there’s other men”</u>
2	Kill Bill by SZA <u>“I just killed my ex (my ex)</u> <u>I still love him, though (I do)”</u>
8	Anti-hero by Taylor Swift	“I might <u>kill</u> my ex, I still <u>love</u> him though” <u>“I have this thing where I get older but just never wiser”</u>

There are three samples of paradox in Song 5. To begin with, the line *“What doesn’t kill me makes me want you more”* (Swift et al., 2023) conveys a paradoxical meaning. It suggests that the challenges and difficult situations here intensify the desire. Additionally, the term “breakable heaven” in the lyrics below suggests a contradiction, as heaven usually is considered unbreakable.

It’s cool, that’s what I tell’em
No rules in breakable heaven

“No rules in breakable heaven” suggests a place or state of being where conventional rules or limitations do not apply. “Breakable heaven” can also be interpreted as a metaphor for a fragile or delicate state of happiness or contentment. This line implies no restrictions or boundaries to what can be done or experienced in this state.

The last sample of paradox in Song 5 is observed in the underlined part of the lyrics below.

*I'm drunk in the back of the car
 And I cried like a baby coming home from the bar (ob)*

Babies are sensitive and vulnerable. They must be safe, sterile, and less crowded for their well-being and health. However, the phrase “baby coming home from the bar” indicates a paradoxical situation.

Another example of paradox can be seen in Song 18. *The “I’ll take it in and let it go”* (Tedder et al., 2022) line in the lyrics is a paradoxical expression. Taking something in and letting something go contradict each other, so the line has a paradoxical meaning.

Finally, Song 6 also contains a sample of paradox:

*But baby keep it to yourself
I don’t wanna know, if you’re playing me (Wayne et al., 2023)*

The paradox in these lines is that the person is suspicious about being played but still does not want to know about it. Even though this person has certain doubts about being cheated on, the underlined lyrics suggest an agreement to stay in this relationship.

3.4. Personification

Our small-scale corpus contains eighteen examples of personification, constituting 9% of the total data. Personification examples appeared in twelve of the songs; ten examples are in the table below, and five will be explained.

Table 6.

Personifications

Song	Name of the Song & Singer(s)	Personification
3	As It Was by Harry Styles	“Holdin’ me back <u>Gravity’s holdin’ me back</u> ” “ <u>Devils roll the dice, angels roll their eyes</u> ”
5	Cruel Summer by Taylor Swift	... “ <u>Killing me slow</u> , out the window I’m always waiting for you to be waiting below”
4	Seven by Jung Kook and Latto	“You wrap around me and <u>you give me life</u> ”
6	Creepin’ by Metro Boomin and The Weeknd	“Keep it on the low Cause <u>my heart can’t take it anymore</u> ”
8	Anti-hero by Taylor Swift	“ <u>When my depression works the graveyard shift</u> ” “ <u>Words, they always win</u> , but I know I’ll lose”
15	Another Love by Tom Odell	... “ <u>My heart is thinking of</u> ” ...
11	Die For You by The Weeknd	“And if somebody hurts you, I wanna fight <u>But my hand’s been broken one too many times</u> ” “I’m finding ways to <u>manipulate the feelin’</u> you’re goin’ through”

Initially, a sample of personification can be seen in the lyrics of Song 3 below:

*Holdin’ me back
Gravity’s holdin’ me back (Styles et al., 2022).*

Gravity is personified here as if it has the ability to hold the speaker back. This personification suggests that something in the speaker's life weighs them down, hindering their progress and impeding efforts to improve their life.

Song 5 contains two examples of personification. Devils and angels are personified in this line: "Devils roll the dice, angels roll their eyes" (Swift et al., 2023). Human-like actions were assigned to devils and angels as if they could roll the dice and their eyes. It is an example of figurative language contrasting the actions of devils and angels. "Devils roll the dice" suggests that devils are taking chances or risks, perhaps engaging in behaviors that are seen as reckless or morally questionable. Rolling dice is often associated with gambling and uncertainty.

On the other hand, "angels roll their eyes" implies that angels are expressing disapproval or skepticism. Rolling one's eyes is a gesture often associated with disbelief or annoyance. In this context, it suggests that angels are observing the actions of the devils with a sense of disdain or disapproval. The phrase highlights the contrast between devils' daring, risk-taking behavior, and angels' more cautious, morally upright demeanor. The second example of personification can be seen in the lyrics of Song 5 below:

*Killing me slow, out the window
I'm always waiting for you to be waiting below*

In this line, time is personified by giving it a human characteristic, "kill," to highlight the emotional burden of waiting. It conveys a sense of emotional longing and the pain of waiting for someone who may not always be there.

Another example of personification can be seen in the line of Song 4 below:

You wrap around me and you give me life (Wotman et al., 2023).

Presenting the abstract concept of "life" as if it is something to be given, suggesting the energy that the partner brings into the relationship is an example of personification. "Giving life" indicates that the presence or actions of this person rejuvenate the speaker, making them feel alive, vibrant, and energized. It suggests that the relationship or connection with this person is essential for the speaker's well-being and happiness.

The last sample of personification is from Song 6. The heart is personified in the underlined part, and human characteristics are attributed to it.

*Keep it on the low
Cause my heart can't take it anymore* (Wayne et al., 2023)

The speaker implies that their emotions are already strained or overwhelmed. They suggest that if whatever they are keeping secret were to become known, it would be emotionally devastating for them. This could imply fear of rejection, betrayal, or further emotional turmoil. Overall, the phrase conveys a sense of vulnerability and a need to protect oneself from potential emotional harm by keeping certain things hidden, and the heart is personified here as the bearer of this emotional challenge.

3.5. Simile

Simile is the fifth most commonly used figurative language in our data. There are thirteen examples of simile in ten of the songs out of twenty-five, constituting 6.5%. Ten of them

can be seen in the table below, and a few of them from various songs will be explained in detail.

Table 7.
Similes

Song	Name of the Song & Singer(s)	Simile
		<u>“Girl, you sweet like Fanta, Fanta”</u>
7	Calm Down by Rema and Selena Gomez “I know say she sabi pass that one (mm-hm) But she feeling insecure <u>“Cause her friends go dey gum her like chewing gum”</u> <u>“He looks up grinning like a devil”</u>
5	Cruel Summer by Taylor Swift “I’m drunk in the back of the car <u>And I cried like a baby coming home from the bar (oh)”</u>
1	Flowers by Miley Cyrus	“We were good, we were gold <u>Kinda dream that can’t be sold”</u>
18	I ain’t Worried by OneRepublic	“I’m living <u>like I’m nine-zeros</u> Got no regrets, even when I’m broke, yeah”
21	Golden Hour by JVKE	<u>“Minutes feel like hours”</u>
23	Paint the Town Red by Doja Cat	<u>“I’m a demon lord”</u>
8	Anti-hero by Taylor Swift	<u>“Did you hear my covert narcissism I disguise as altruism Like some kind of congressman? (Tale as old as time)”</u>
25	Snooze by SZA	<u>“In the droptop ride with you, I feel like Scarface (Scarface)”</u>

Song 7 bears two examples of simile. Both of these similes were provided by using the word “like.” In the first line, the girl’s sweetness is compared to Fanta: “Girl, you sweet like Fanta, Fanta” (Ikubor et al., 2022). Fanta is a trendy brand that produces sugary cold drinks like orange juice. The speaker finds the girl as sweet as Fanta beverages, and this likening is provided through " like " as a preposition. It is used to draw a comparison between “girl” and “Fanta,” suggesting that her sweetness is similar to that of a drink. This structure is commonly used in English to make comparisons. The latter example of simile in this song is in the underlined part of the lyrics below:

*I know say she sabi pass that one (mm-hm)
 But she feeling insecure
‘Cause her friends go dey gum her like chewing gum*

Stating that her friends do not leave her alone or stick to her like a chewing gum is a simile. Correspondingly, Song 5 makes use of similes in a parallel manner, utilizing the word “like.” The primary sample of simile is in the line “He looks up grinning like a devil,” in which the grin on the person’s face is compared to a devil. This line suggests that when “he” looks up, he is grinning mischievously or cunningly, reminiscent of the way one might imagine a devil grinning. It implies a sly or mischievous expression on his face, possibly indicating that he is up to something or finding amusement in a situation. The second example of simile in this song is also provided by “like.”

*I’m drunk in the back of the car
And I cried like a baby coming home from the bar (oh) (Swift et al., 2023)*

These lyrics depict a scene where someone is intoxicated in the backseat of a car, likely feeling emotionally overwhelmed. The underlined part of the lyrics suggests that despite being

intoxicated, the person is crying heavily, similar to how a baby might cry. This implies deep emotional distress or vulnerability, possibly triggered by something experienced at the bar or related to the state of being drunk. It portrays a moment of intense emotional release and vulnerability.

Lastly, Song 1 also provides an example of a simile, as seen in the following lines.

We were good, we were gold
Kinda dream that can't be sold (Cyrus *et al.*, 2022)

The speaker implies that their relationship was priceless and like a dream. Their experience or relationship is so special and meaningful that it cannot be bought or replicated. It is like a dream that is beyond material worth or commercial value. Overall, these lines convey the idea of something cherished and irreplaceable.

3.6. Metonymy

Our study has nine metonymy examples appearing in six songs, constituting 4.5% of the figurative language samples. All the metonymy examples samples in our data can be seen in the table below, and six of them will be explained in detail.

Table 8.

Metonymies

Song	Name of the Song & Singer(s)	Metonymy
23	Paint the Town Red by Doja Cat	This <u>Margiel</u> ' don't come with no jealousy"
24	Sweater Weather by The Neighbourhood	"One love, two <u>mouths</u> " "P1 cleaner than your church shoes, ah"
16	Starboy by The Weeknd, Daft Punk	"All red <u>Lamb</u> ' just to tease you, ah" "Pull off in that <u>Roadster SV</u> , ah" "I'm in the blue <u>Mulsanne</u> bumping New Edition"
10	I'm Good (Blue) by David Guetta and Bebe Rexha	"And I, I don't need to sit in <u>VIP</u> "
20	Last Night by Morgan Wallen	"Last bottle of Jack, we <u>split a fifth</u>
21	Golden Hour by JVKE	"It was just two lovers Sittin' in the car, <u>listening to Blonde</u> "

To begin with, Song 23 has one example of metonymy: "This Margiel' don't come with no jealousy" (Dlamini, 2023). In this line, Margiel is a luxurious clothing brand representing success and a particular lifestyle. This one brand name is used to express the whole lifestyle. Likewise, Song 24 also includes one sample of metonymy. The underlined word in this line, "One love, two mouths," does not solely stand for its primary meaning, mouth (Rutherford *et al.*, 2012). The speaker intends two people with this word. Therefore, a part of something (mouth) is utilized to represent the whole (individual).

Four examples of metonymy were found in Song 16, which can be seen in the underlined words in the lyrics below.

P1 cleaner than your church shoes, ab
 ...
All red Lamb' just to tease you, ab

Pull off in that Roadster SV, ab

I'm in the blue Mulsanne bumping New Edition (Tesfaye et al., 2016)

In all these lines, the speaker highlights being wealthy through different car brands (P1, Lamb', Roadster, and Mulsanne). All the underlined words represent fancy cars that rich people can afford. Instead of stating this wealthy lifestyle overtly, the speaker lists a number of car names so as to demonstrate it.

3.7. Synecdoche

Synecdoche is similar to metonymy, yet a synecdoche is when an aspect of anything is used to represent the entire thing or the other way around (Kennedy & Gioia, 1994). Synecdoche has the same frequency as metonymy, which is nine and 4.5% of the data. Synecdoche examples are observed in five songs in total, and all of them will be presented here, but six of them will be explained in detail.

Table 9.
Synecdoches

Song	Name of the Song & Singer(s)	Synecdoche
4	Seven by Jung Kook & Latto	“Goin’ ‘til the sun up, we ain’t getting’ no sleep Seven days a week, seven different <u>sheets</u> ”
15	Another Love by Tom Odell	“And I’d sing a song that’d be just ours But I sang ‘em all to <u>another heart</u> ” “Got you ridin round in <u>all types of benz’s and rovers</u> Girl you used to ride in a rinky dink”
6	Creepin’ by The Weeknd & 21 Savage	“I’m the one put you in <u>Eliante</u> (on God)” “ <u>Fashion Nova</u> model, I put you on the runway (on God)”
5	Cruel Summer by Taylor Swift	“And it’s new, <u>the shape of your body</u> ”
12	Unholy by Sam Smith and Kim Petras	“Mmm, daddy, daddy, if you want it, drop the add’y (yuh) Give me love, give me <u>Fendi</u> , my <u>Balenciaga</u> daddy” “And he, he get me <u>Prada</u> , get me <u>Miu Miu</u> like Rihanna (ah)”

In the first sample,

Goin’ ‘til the sun up, we ain’t gettin’ no sleep
Seven days a week, seven different sheets

sheets represent intimate nights and beds they spend time in. Sheets represent a part of something bigger-bed. That is an example of synecdoche. Similarly, in the second sample, “another heart” represents “another person” (Odell, 2012). This example of synecdoche is a common representation. Love is generally associated with the heart. Thus, when *heart* is used

similarly to these lyrics, it represents another person and the romantic connection between them.

*And I'd sing a song that'd be just ours
But I sang 'em all to another heart*

Song 6 has four examples of synecdoche. In the first example, Benz's and rovers represent all kinds of luxurious car brand names. The speaker highlights that the girl's financial situation was not very bright before meeting him. He presented a luxurious life to her.

*Got you ridin round in all types of benz's and rovers
Girl you used to ride in a rinky dink (Wayne et al., 2023)*

Similarly, the underlined word "Eliante" in the line, "I'm the one put you in Eliante (on God)" represents all kinds of luxurious jewelry. Eliante is a very high-end jewelry brand that is especially famous for its diamond designs. Similarly, the speaker underlines the wealthier touch he made on the girl's lifestyle. Another example of synecdoche from this song touches upon the fame the woman achieved with him. In this line, "Fashion Nova model, I put you on the runway (on God)" Fashion Nova is women's top online fashion store. Lastly, chanaynay, in this line, "You were rocking coach bags, got you chanaynay," is a slang word used to refer to the famous brand Chanel. Here, it represents all kinds of luxurious brands.

All in all, all four samples from Song 6 stressed the improvement in the lifestyle of the woman and the better financial opportunities that the man offered to her. The songwriter made this change more vivid and obvious with the help of synecdoche. The songwriter made the lyrics more comprehensible by providing the listeners with all these famous and elegant brand names.

3.8. Pun

Pun is one of our data's least frequent figurative language types (2.5%). Only five examples of it were found in four songs. Song 21 has two examples of pun.

*My radiant beam in the night
.....
She's got glitter for skin (Lawson & Lawson, 2022)*

Radiant has two meanings; the first one is "bright," and the second one is "happy." Here, it may have both meanings, such as an example of a pun in the first line. Secondly, glitter may mean the actual decoration material; instead of having skin, she may be composed of glitter.

In the lines of Song 22:

Georgia, wrap me up in all your (Sanchez, 2021)

Georgia may refer to the state, the country, or a woman. This ambiguity and dual use of the word is an example of a pun. Similarly, there is uncertainty about what "peach" refers to in the fourth data.

*You was out of reach
You was at the farmer's market with your perfect peach (Rowe et al., 2022)*

With the underlined part of the lyrics, the speaker may mean a real peach or his new girlfriend, which is not overtly expressed. Finally, there is a play on words in “Hit me up and P'ma Cha Cha Slide” in Song 4, where “hit me up” means to contact, but it also integrates a dance reference, the “Cha Cha Slide.” These samples of play on words or dual meanings explicitly exemplify pun.

3.9. Transferred Epithet

Three examples of the transferred epithet in three songs make up 1.5% of the entire corpus. For instance, “It’s a cruel summer” in Song 5 shows a shift of the modifier from the animate to the inanimate- cruelty to summer. Normally, cruelty is connoted with humans or animals. It attributes a violent and negative action to the bearer of it. However, this “animate” feature is associated with “inanimate” summer in this line.

Similarly, in Song 6 and Song 21,

How you go from housewife to a sneaky link (Song 6) (Wayne et al., 2023)
She’s got glow on her face

A glorious look in her eyes (Song 21) (Lawson & Lawson, 2022)

adjectives “sneaky” and “glorious” were used differently than their traditional usage. The adjective “sneaky” is associated with people, but in the second data, it modifies sexual activity. That is the transferred epithet sample in this line. Lastly, in Song 21, the adjective “glorious” is transferred to a noun that is not logically related.

3.10. Apostrophe

The apostrophe is one of the two lowest figures for speech type in our data (1%). It appeared only two times in two songs. The first example of the apostrophe is in Song 21:

Can you even imagine
Fallin’ like I did? (Lawson & Lawson, 2022)

In these lines, the speaker talks to an absent person by not specifically stating who they are. The speaker might be addressing an audience that is not present there, or a hero or imaginary friend, or someone known from the past. The ambiguity and uncertainty of the addressee make this sentence an example of an apostrophe. The following data is from Song 22:

Georgia, wrap me up in all your
I want you in my arms (Sanchez, 2021)

These lines include a group of figurative language types. Firstly, there is a pun because Georgia may refer to the state, the country, or a woman, and if it refers to a state or country, there is personification as well, and also an apostrophe because the speaker directly talks to an inanimate object.

3.11. Understatement

The second least frequent figurative language type in our data is an understatement (1%), appearing two times in two different songs. Both of the examples are displayed below.

In the lines of Song 2, “Uh, I just killed my ex (my ex) Not the best idea (idea),” killing is made less important than what it actually is by stating it is “not the best idea” (Rowe, Bisel, & Lang, 2022). Killing someone is a brutal crime that cannot be associated with “the best idea”. In this line, the songwriter understates the gravity of the incident.

The other example is observed in Song 16, where understatement refers to expensive cars as toys: “None of these toys on lease too, ah” (Tesfaye et al., 2016). In this line, the songwriter is trying to make them less important than they are. Naming these precious cars as toys and devaluing them can be associated with the speaker not valuing things of high material value and seeing them as temporary toys.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be asserted that globally popular songs are notably rich in figures of speech, as this small-scale corpus study revealed. The presence of two hundred examples within just twenty-five songs suggests that songwriters frequently employ figures of speech. Additionally, the fact that these songs are among the most replayed and listened to of the year implies that listeners worldwide greatly appreciate the covert expression of thoughts and emotions by songwriters who prefer a multi-layered unfolding of the lyrics rather than an overt conveying of meaning to the listeners. In the present study, all eleven figures of speech outlined in Kennedy and Gioia (1994) were identified in the compositions. Metaphor emerges as the most prevalent figure of speech type with a frequency of 76, followed by hyperbole with 40 occurrences. The frequency distribution of other types is as follows: paradox (n=23), personification (n=18), simile (n=13), metonymy (n=9), synecdoche (n=9), pun (n=5), transferred epithet (n=3), apostrophe (n=2), and understatement (n=2). The study of Sondakh et al. (2023) on the figures of speech used in one of Demi Lovato’s albums also yielded similar results to our research. Metaphor was the predominant figurative language, followed by hyperbole. Their analyses revealed 56 examples of figures of speech, 27 of which were metaphors and 19 of which were hyperbole. Similarly to our study, simile and personification were less common than metaphor and hyperbole. Likewise, the occurrence of metaphor was also the highest in the study of Santika and Syafryadin (2023), with thirteen Taylor Swift songs.

Contrary to the findings of our study, Teja et al. (2022) found simile and hyperbole to be the most frequently used figures of speech types, even though the number of figurative language samples was very limited in their study. Similarly, in the study of Yastanti et al. (2018) with Linkin Park songs, hyperbole emerged as the most prevalent type of figure of speech. However, their sample was also limited when compared to our study. The rich use of figures of speech in songs enables a more creative and imaginative way to express feelings and emotions, and this helps listeners bond with the music on a deeper level. Moreover, this creative and artistic expression facilitates the memorability of the lyrics, making them catchy and easier to remember. Imagery is another contribution of figurative language to the composition by helping the audience paint a picture in their minds with vivid symbolism. Moreover, figures of speech are often open to diverse interpretations with their ambiguous nature, which allows listeners to relate to their own experiences and makes the lyrics unique to them. Last but not least, figures of speech assist songwriters in commenting on societal, cultural, and political issues without being overly explicit. For instance, Balyemez and Arıkan (2019) observed that Turkish-German rap artists express their reaction to the discriminatory and exclusionary aspects of the dominant German culture. Additionally, the language they use in their songs is structured to include other minorities. Hence, it can be concluded that

well-crafted figures of speech play a crucial role in adding layers of meaning and creativity, thereby sustaining the effectiveness and memorability of songs across generations.

When it comes to the educational implications of using these compositions in the context of foreign language teaching and learning, they can also be accepted as rich and valuable sources. Similar findings were obtained by Türkmen and Cesur (2024) in their study on using internationalized children's songs with young English language learners. Due to the songs' essential qualities—such as their “age-appropriateness, repetition, and high recall value” (p. 15)—they provide educators with essential considerations. Furthermore, instructors looking to incorporate songs into various learning situations will find a useful toolkit in the highlighted themes, which range from imperative phrases to life-related elements. Song lyrics can be an effective instructional resource for figures of speech. They can be used to grab student interest and provide further figurative language examples in the classroom (Richards & Lockhart, 1996, p. 117). Song lyrics, including various figures of language, are also invaluable supplies for exposing learners to words and expressions beyond everyday conversation. They also provide a context for the learners, which allows them to understand how these expressions are used in real-life situations. What is more, since figures of speech convey messages about the target cultures and societal norms, they help learners gain insights into these social aspects of the language they are learning. This, in turn, helps them build empathy and understanding towards their lifestyles and values, and it also promotes cultural awareness, making the language learning process more meaningful and holistic. As Türkmen and Cesur (2024) suggest, integrating such music surpasses linguistic barriers, fostering global awareness and empathy among students. Educators can leverage these findings to create dynamic and interactive language learning environments that enhance linguistic proficiency and cultivate a deep understanding of diverse cultures. Finally, music, in its nature, is one of the most motivating and engaging tools. Popular songs and music in a curriculum may help boost the learners' motivation to a greater extent.

In addition, to become proficient users of the target language, especially for understanding and interpreting literary texts and becoming influential writers, EFL learners' familiarity with and exposure to the use of figures of speech are indispensable. The high frequency of the metaphors in the data suggests that metaphor is one of the most common ways of expressing feelings and conveying meaning stylistically and effectively. Understanding the chemistry of metaphor and making students realize its existence and power will be a great opportunity and improvement for English language teachers, not only in terms of comprehending and internalizing the formal structure of the language but also in terms of noticing its power as a form of expression. Even though it is easy to use and understand metaphors in the native language for many, getting the meaning behind the metaphorical expression for L2 learners is not always as easy as it seems. Therefore, EFL teachers' presenting metaphorical expressions in their classes and explaining the hidden meaning behind them will carry the comprehension and acquisition of English by the L2 learners beyond a basic and introductory level. Furthermore, the high frequency of hyperbole in the song lyrics reveals that songwriters highly resort to hyperbole to impress the listeners dramatically and show the depth, greatness, and importance of their feelings by using exaggerated expressions.

Ethical Issues

The authors confirm that the study does not need ethics committee approval according to the research integrity rules in their country (Date of Confirmation: 20/05/2024).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Al-Qudsy, W. B. (2016). *A stylistic analysis of figures of speech in the Jakarta Post headlines under the issue of KPK vs. POLRI* (Unpublished undergraduate thesis). Yogyakarta State University, Faculty of Languages and Arts, English Education Department.
- Arp, T. R., & Perrine, L. (2004). *Sound and sense: An introduction to poetry* (11th ed.). Boston MA: Thomson Learning.
- Balyemez, H., & Arikan, A. (2019). Yeni bir lehçeye doğru: Güncel Türk-Alman rap müziğinde dil kullanımlarının deyişbilimsel bir incelemesi. In *IV. Uluslararası Türk-Alman İlişkileri Sempozyumu*, Antalya, Turkey.
- Barung, L., Pratiwi, D. P. E., & Juniarta, I. W. (2023). Types of figurative language found in Coldplay song lyrics. *ELYSLAN: The Journal of English Literature, Linguistics and Translation Studies*, 3(1), 31–40. <https://doi.org/10.36733/elysian.v3i1.4405>
- Clarke, J. C. (1982). *I Wanna Be Yours* [Recorded by Arctic Monkeys] [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/Arctic-monkeys-i-wanna-be-yours-lyrics>.
- Cyrus, M., Hein, G. A. & Pollack, M. (2022). *Flowers* [Recorded by Miley Cyrus] [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/Miley-cyrus-flowers-lyrics>
- Dancygier, B., & Sweetser, E. (2014). *Figurative language*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Dlamini, A. Z. (2023). *Paint The Town Red* [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/Doja-cat-paint-the-town-red-lyrics>
- Dutta, B. K., & Talukder, A. A. (2022). A study on figurative language in William Blake's "The Echoing Green". *Prime University Journal*, 16(1), 1–6.
- Genetti, C. (Ed.). (2014). *How languages work: An introduction to language and linguistics*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Glucksberg, S. (2001). *Understanding figurative language: From metaphors to idioms*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Ikubor, D., Vibe, A., & Hunter, M. (2022). *Calm Down (Remix)* [Recorded by Rema & Selena Gomez] [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/Rema-and-selena-gomez-calm-down-remix-lyrics>
- Joshi, M. (2014). *Dictionary of literal words: Vocabulary building*. London: Manic Joshi Publishers.
- Julianto, S. L., Sedeng, I. N., & Mulyana, N. (2023). Figurative language in the song lyrics of Billie Eilish "Don't Smile At Me". *ULJL ALBAB: Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin*, 2(10), 4903–4911. <https://doi.org/10.56799/jim.v2i10.2257>
- Kennedy, X. J., & Gioia, D. (1994). *An introduction to poetry* (8th ed.). New York, NY: Harper Collins College Publishers.
- Kennedy, X.J., & Gioia, D. (1995). *Literature: An introduction to fiction, poetry, and drama* (6th ed.). New York, NY: Harper Collins College Publishers.
- Lambert, V. A., & Lambert, C. E. (2012). Editorial: Qualitative descriptive research: An acceptable design. *Pacific Rim International Journal of Nursing Research*, 14(4), 255–256. Retrieved from <https://he02.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/PRIJNR/article/view/5805>

- Lawson, J., & Lawson, Z. (2022). *Golden Hour* [Recorded by Jacop Lawson (Jvke)] [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/Jvke-golden-hour-lyrics>
- Leech, G. (Ed). (1981). *Semantics*. New Zealand: Penguin Book.
- Leech, G. N. (2013). *A linguistic guide to English poetry*. London, UK: Routledge.
- Mayring, P. (2000). Qualitative content analysis. *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 1(2), Article 20. Retrieved from <http://www.qualitative-research.net/index.php/fqs/article/view/1089/2385>
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *An expanded sourcebook: Qualitative data analysis*. London: Sage Publication.
- Monga, A. (2024, May 17). Spotify statistics for 2024: User, subscriber, revenue. Retrieved from <https://insights.vaizle.com/spotify-statistics/#:~:text=How%20many%20monthly%20listeners%20on,increased%20to%20574%20M%20globally>
- Odell, T. (2012). *Another Love* [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/Tom-odell-another-love-lyrics>
- Pope, C., Ziebland, S., & Mays, N. (2006). Analysing qualitative data. In C. Pope & N. Mays (Eds.), *Qualitative research in health care* (3rd ed., pp. 63–81). Oxford, UK: Blackwell Publishing.
- Quinn, A. (1982). *Figures of speech: 60 ways to turn a phrase*. Utah, UT: Gibbs Smith Publisher.
- Regmi, L. R. (2014). Analysis and use of figures of speech. *Journal of NELTA Surkhet*, 4, 76–80. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jns.v4i0.12864>
- Richards, J. C., & Lockhart, C. (1996). *Reflective language teaching in the second language classroom*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Rowe, S., Bisel, R., & Lang, C. (2022). *Kill Bill* [Recorded by SZA] [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/Sza-kill-bill-lyrics>
- Rutherford, J., Abels, Z., & Freedman, J. (2012). *Sweater Weather* [Recorded by The Neighbourhood] [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/The-neighbourhood-sweater-weather-lyrics>
- Sanchez, S. (2021). *Until I Found You (Em Beihold Version)* [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/Stephen-sanchez-and-em-beihold-until-i-found-you-em-beihold-version-lyrics>
- Santika, P., & Syafryadin, S. (2023). An analysis of figurative language in song lyrics of the album “Midnights” by Taylor Swift. *Wiralodra English Journal*, 7(1),14–28. <https://doi.org/10.31943/wej.v7i1.189>
- Sondakh, R., Samola, N., & Damopolii, V. L. (2023). An analysis of figurative language in Demi Lovato’s song lyrics. *JoTELL: Journal of Teaching English, Linguistics, and Literature*, 2(4), 468–491.
- Spotify. (2023, November 29). Top Tracks of 2023. Retrieved from <https://open.spotify.com/playlist/37i9dQZF1DX18jTM2l2fjY?si=z4qhxLxoT7CuCNEEmWDkPw&pi=e-kFRwjgYKRpiy&nd=1&dlsi=5009004fc2174f9>
- Styles, H., Hull, T., & Johnson, T. (2022). *As It Was* [Recorded by Harry Styles] [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/Harry-styles-as-it-was-lyrics>
- Swift, T., Antonoff, J., & Clark, A. (2023). *Cruel Summer* [Recorded by Taylor Swift] [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/Taylor-swift-cruel-summer-lyrics>
- Tedder, R., Kutzle, B., Spry, T., Eriksson, J., Moren, P., & Yttling, B. (2022). *I Ain’t Worried* [Recorded by OneRepublic] [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/Onerepublic-i-aint-worried-lyrics>
- Teja, N. S., Utami, N. M. V., & Juniarta, I. W. (2022). Uncover the meaning of figurative language in the selected songs. *Journal of Language and Pragmatics Studies*, 1(1), 32–39.

- Tesfaye, A., Homem-Christo, G. M., Bangalter, T., McKinney, M., Walter, H., & Quenneville, J. (2016). *Starboy* [Recorded by The Weeknd] [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/The-weeknd-starboy-lyrics>
- Tesfaye, A., McKinney, M., Rhars, M., Wiggins, D., Høiberg M., Walsh, W. T., & Walter, H. (2017). *Die For You* [Recorded by The Weeknd] [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/The-weeknd-die-for-you-lyrics>
- Thwala, J. J., Khoza, S. S., Lusenga, N. M., & Mayisela, J. J. (2019). An analysis of figures of speech in two selected languages: English and Siswati. *International Journal of Arts Humanities and Social Sciences Studies*, 4(6), 1–8.
- Türkmen, G. N., & Cesur, K. (2024). Internationalization of a regional children's song for teaching English to young learners. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 18(1), 1–17. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10876861>
- Vaismoradi, M., Turunen, H., & Bondas, T. (2013). Content analysis and thematic analysis: Implications for conducting a qualitative descriptive study. *Nursing & Health Sciences*, 15(3), 398–405. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nhs.12048>
- Wayne, L., Tesfaye, A., Abraham-Joseph, S., Quenneville, J., Johnson, P. L., Lenox, J., Winans, M., Bhraonain, E. N., Sermon, E., Smith, P., Hawkins, C., Jones, M., Ryan, N., & Ryan, R. (2023). *Creepin* [Recorded by Metro Boomin, The Weeknd, and 21 Savage] [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/Metro-boomin-the-weeknd-and-21-savage-creepin-lyrics>
- Wotman, A., Walter, H. R., Bellion, J. D., Stephens, A. M., & Thomas, T. (2023). *Seven*. [Recorded by Jungkook] [Lyrics]. Retrieved from <https://genius.com/Jung-kook-seven-explicit-ver-lyrics>
- Yastanti, U., Suhendar, J., & Pratama, R. M. D. (2018). Figurative language in song lyrics of Linkin Park. *Progressive Journal*, 13(2), 95–106.